

Conference Abstract

New data on the genus *Papillifera* W. Hartmann, 1842 (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae) in Sicily (Italy)

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Abstract

Papillifera papillaris (O.F. Müller, 1774) is a door snail (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae) with Graciliaria clausilial apparatus, autochthonous in southern Italy, Sicily and Maltese Islands, but that has been widespread in the western Mediterranean region.

In Sicily, *P. papillaris* is widely distributed and relatively diverse and this led in the 1800s to the description of numerous taxa. Some of these taxa are considered valid subspecies, while other taxa have not been revised in recent times. In the present work the taxa described for the genus *Papillifera* W. Hartmann, 1842 in Sicily are re-examined and the distribution of the subspecies is redefined.

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